

EXPLORING THE RELATIONSHIP OF PARENTS' SOCIO-ECONOMIC BACKGROUND AND STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR UNIVERSITY EXTENSION SERVICE AGENDA

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ABSTRACT

Having been trapped with the notion that education is terms of what money can buy, this study aimed to investigate the relationship between parents' socioeconomic status and the academic performance of Grade 11 students in Mindanao State University – Sulu Senior High School. To achieve this, a sample of 130 respondents from Grade 11 were selected using random sampling technique and checklist questionnaires were administered to the respondents. The collected data was analyzed using Frequency for counts and percentage of the variables, Mean, One-Way ANOVA as well as Chi-Square Test. Results revealed that majority of the students' parents were farmers or fisher folks, with a monthly income of P5,000.00 and below and managed to finished secondary education. It was also found that students' academic performance may vary heavily with the influence of their parents' income, and their educational attainment also showed a relationship. Whereby, parents' occupation has no significant difference and relation to how students perform in school. Therefore, schools can use the findings of this study in order to implement policies or programs to reduce financial inequality as well as educational disparities among students from diverse backgrounds in Sulu.

Keywords: *Socioeconomic Status, Academic Performance, Parents, MSU – Sulu, Extension Service*

INTRODUCTION

Understanding the complexities of 21st century issues in education is quite very challenging. Living in a third world country like Philippines where most parents are almost limping with the quagmire of financial woes and misery, quality education is no doubt as far from reality (Ordoñez, 2015; Abdurahman & Omar, 2021).

Issue on parents' socio-economic status are undeniably facing education realities. This imparts the idea that the resources and status of an individual may possess greater sphere of influence in the educational playing field. It is a truism that families with great wealth could access proper services and privileges in education contrary to those who have not. According to Muhammad, Edi & Hermantu (2022), the different economic status of parents will directly cause different academic achievements of the students thus even lead to educational disparities.

Meanwhile, academic performance is interpreted as how students perform in school academically. Ellie Williams (2018) said that academic performance is not only reflected by the general point average (GPA) but also includes factors such as good leadership skills and eagerness to excel academically. Education is undeniably interconnected with social and economic structures as it serves as the navigator of social mobility, which emphasizes the importance of understanding the factors that may influence the students' academic paths (World Bank, 2016).

Many studies have looked upon the connection between these variables. It shows that students from wealthier families often have more privileges like private tutoring and conducive environment for learning, which imply that being born rich is actually a better sign of adult success (Carnevale et al., 2019). On the other hand, because of low situation of socioeconomic status of some individuals, it would be difficult to purchase needed materials and provide support. Thus, the hindering the quality of education the students should have in the first place (Esther, 2018).

For several decades now, school administrators have to cope with litany of changes vis-a-vis the ever-evolving educational dynamism in the playing field (Isa J., Madjid J., et al., 2024; A. Abdurahman, 2023; Abdurahman et al., 2024) . Researches relating socioeconomic status to academic performance were conducted in developed countries and urban areas, lacking any susceptible studies in rural or remote areas such as Sulu, Philippines. For this reason, this study aims to uncover how social and economic factors may influence the learning performance of the Grade 11 students attending MSU-Sulu Senior High School, a public institution in Patikul, Sulu. Understanding this dynamic is crucial for educators and administrators to identify strategies in order to address the rampant educational inequalities and aim to narrow the achievement gap among students with diverse backgrounds.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to figure out how parents' socioeconomic status relates to the academic performance of Grade 11 Students of MSU – Sulu Senior High School.

Therefore, the intention of this study is to directly answer the following questions:

- 1.What is the profile of the Grade 11 Students of MSU – Sulu Senior High School in terms of parents' income, educational attainment, and occupation?
- 2.What is the level of academic performance of these students?
- 3.Is there a significant difference on the academic performance when they are grouped according to parents' income, educational attainment, and occupation?
- 4.Is there any significant relationship between parents' socioeconomic status on the academic performance of the students?

METHODOLOGY

This section discusses the research methodology of the study which includes the research locale, respondents of the study, data collection, research instrument, and data gathering procedure and statistical techniques and scope and delimitation of the study.

Research Locale

The researchers conducted the study at MSU – Sulu Senior High School Department, by means of a room-to-room survey starting from the Old Biology Building, down to the main building's first floor to third floor of each room. This was conducted following the 3rd quarter of the institution's academic year 2023-2024. Mindanao State University – Sulu is a public educational university, founded in 1974 by the government to advance the state of education in the Province of Sulu, situated at Capitol Site, Patikul, Sulu. The choice of the setting of this study was inspired by the following reasons: First MSU-Sulu is the only university in the province of Sulu catering senior high students from diverse financial background. And second, the findings of this study could somehow help the administration in formulating programs that inspired inclusiveness of all constituents.

Respondents of the Study

The MSU – Sulu Senior High School Department has a total of 1,055 population of Grade 11 students which composed of 13 sections for the Academic Year 2023 – 2024. The researchers surveyed 10 randomly picked participants coming from each section of the Grade 11 students resulting to a total of 130 respondents. The researchers have decided to take these students as respondents of the study for the following reasons: First, the results derived from study will somehow become a baseline data for the faculty members to craft programs and policies to augment students' academic performance. Second, this will also help struggling students who are financially handicapped to strive

much harder to cope with the performance of those students coming from well off family. Third, the researchers found it accessible to conduct the study since they are also enrolled in the same institution.

Data Collection

The data collection process for this study required a systematic and collaborative approach of the researchers. Initially, formal permission was obtained from the Director of Senior High School Department to conduct the survey. At the same time, the researchers ensured that the research meets academic standards and any concerns was formally address through regular consultation with the thesis adviser. A comprehensive questionnaire based on an extensive literature review was developed and tested for clarity. A stratified random sampling technique was used to select 10 respondents from each of the 13 sections of Grade 11, resulting in a total of 130 respondents, with consents obtained from the advisers and respondents. The researchers conducted a robust statistical analysis after the collection of data to determine the relationship of parents' socioeconomic status and educational achievement of students.

Instrumentation

The researchers used a survey method to support and acquire more necessary data to the study. The survey instrument used was a checklist questionnaire formulated by the researchers to evaluate the result and determine if there is a correlation between the students' academic performance to their parents' social and economic status.

The checklist questionnaire was divided into two parts. The first part contains the students' demographic profile, in which their name and academic performance from the 1st semester was collected. Whilst, the demographic profile of parents, including their name (optional) and socioeconomic status, such as income, educational attainment, and occupation was on the second part of the questionnaire.

Statistical Techniques

To tackle the research questions and meet the objectives, various statistical tools were utilized for analyzing the collected data from respondents. Concerning the first problem (SOP 1), the researchers used frequency to depict students' profiles in terms of their parents' income, educational attainment, and occupation. This approach involves counting students in each category or range and presenting the data through tables and graphs. For the second problem statement (SOP 2), the average mean was applied to gauge students' academic performance based on their first semester grades. This method allows the calculation of the average grade or score, facilitating a comparison with academic excellence standards. In the third statement of the problem (SOP 3), One-Way ANOVA was utilized to answer the difference of the academic performance based on the profile of their parents. Finally, the fourth problem (SOP 4) used Chi-Square Test to assess the strength and direction of the association by assessing whether parents'

socioeconomic status has a positive or negative relationship on the academic performance of students. These statistical tools provided a thorough and systematic data analysis to address the research questions.

Scope and Delimitation

This study explored the relationship of students' academic performance in and the parents' socio-economic in Mindanao State University-Suly Senior High School Department. This investigation exposed how various factors associated with Socio Economic Status such as parents' income, level of educational qualification, and occupation influence students academic performance determined by the general point average (GPA) of the students. Furthermore, this investigation was limited only to the Grade 11 students of MSU-Sulu senior high school. While considering the potential influence of family status of on the students' academic performance, this study did not dig deeply to consider factors like family structure, students' study techniques, and learning preferences. Time element was also considered a potential limitation of this investigation.

RESULTS

A. Students' Demographic Profile

Table 1: presents the profile of the students in MSU-Sulu Senior High School in terms of their parents' monthly income, educational attainment and occupation. As to monthly income, the majority (62.3%) have an income of P5,000.00 and below. As to their educational attainment, majority (18.5%) finished the secondary education. Lastly, as to the parents' occupation, majority (30.0%) were farmers or fisher folks.

Table 1: Students' Demographic Profile

Parents' Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage
P5,000.00 and below	81	62.3
P5,001.00 to P10,000.00	18	13.8
P10,001.00 to P15,000.00	7	5.4
P15,001.00 to P25,000.00	11	8.5
P25,001.00 to P50,000.00	10	7.7
P50,001.00 and above	3	2.3
Parents' Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
No Formal Education	17	13.1
Elementary/Primary Education	18	13.8

Finished Elementary Education	7	5.4
High School/Secondary Education	22	16.9
Finished Secondary Education	24	18.5
Collage/Tertiary Education	23	17.7
Finished Tertiary Education	19	14.6
Total	130	100.0

Parents' Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Government Employee	25	19.2
OFW	7	5.4
Farmer/Fisher Folk	39	30.0
Businessman	15	11.5
Vendor/Salesperson	20	15.4
Others	24	18.5
Total	130	100.0

B. Level of Academic Performance

Table 2 provides the result of level of the academic performance of Grade 11 students in MSU - Sulu. The overall mean is 87.71% with a verbal description of Very Satisfactory (85-89).

Table 2: Level of the Students' Academic Performance

Academic Performance	Mean	Verbal Description
Grade 11 students	87.71%	Very Satisfactory

Legend: Outstanding = 90-100; Very Satisfactory = 85-89; Satisfactory = 80-84; Fairly Satisfactory = 75-79; and Did Not Meet Expectation = 74 or below

C. Difference on the Students' Academic Performance According to Parents' Socioeconomic Status

Table 3 depicts the significant difference of students' academic performance according to parents' socio-economic status. The results revealed that $p = .14$.

Table 3 : Difference of Academic Performance According to Parents' Socioeconomic Status

Measure	P5,000.00 below	and	P5,001.00 P10,000.00	–	P10,001.00 P15,000.00	–	P15,001.00 P25,000.00	–
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>

Monthly Income	86.7	3.9	89.5	2.7	89.8	3.3	89.0	5.5
	P25,001.00 – P50,000.00		P50,001.00 and above		F(5, 124)	p-value		
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>				
	86.6	2.4	90	3.4	2.984	.014		

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

D. Difference on the Academic Performance According to Parents Educational Qualification

Table. 4 illustrates the significant difference on the students' academic performance according to educational qualification of the parents. The result is the following: $F(6, 123)$, $p = .099$.

Table 4 : Difference of Academic Performance According to Parents' Educational Attainment

Measure	No formal Education		Elementary/Primary Education		Finished Elementary Education		High School / Secondary Education	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Educational Attainment	86.5	3.6	87.2	3.4	88.6	2.2	86.5	4.8
Finished Secondary Education	College Tertiary Education		/ Finished Education		Tertiary		F(6, 123)	p-value
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1.829	.099
	86.6	3.1	88.7	3.8	89.3	4.6		

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

E. Significant Difference of the Students' Academic Performance According to Parents Occupation.

Table 5 illumines the significant difference on the students academic performance according to their parents' occupation such as: Government employee, OFW, Farmer/Fisherfolks' Businessman, Vendor/ salesperson, etc. The result was , $F(5, 124)$, $p = .113$.

Table 5: Difference of Academic Performance with Parents Occupation

Measure	Government Employee		OFW		Farmer/Fisher Folk		Businessman	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Occupation								

88.4	4.2	86.8	4.0	86.1	3.5	87.4	3.2
Vendor/Salesperson		Others		F(5, 124)		p-value	
<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>				
88.6	4.2	88.3	4.1	1.824		.113	

and above

Note. χ^2 = Chi-square value

*Significant at $p=0.05$

Relationship of Students' Academic Performance and Parents Socio Economic Status

This section portrays the relationship of students' academic performance and parents' socio economic status in terms of monthly income, parents' occupation and their educational qualification.

A. Relationship of Students' Academic Performance and Parents' Monthly Income

Table 6 sheds light on the relationship between students' academic performance with the parents' monthly income. The parents' income ranges from 5,000 and below to 50, 000 and above. The results revealed the following: $\chi^2(15, N=130) = 26.095, p = .037$.

Table 6. Relationship of students' academic performance and parents' monthly income

Parameters		Level of Academic Performance				χ^2	p
		Fairly Satisfactory (75-79)	Satisfactory (80-84)	Very Satisfactory (85-89)	Outstanding (90-100)		
Monthly Income	P5,000.00 and below and above	2	29	33	17	26.095	.037

Note. χ^2 = Chi-square value

*Significant at $p=0.05$

B. Relationship of Students' Academic Performance and Parents' Educational Qualification

Table 7 spouses the relationship of students' academic performance with the parents' educational qualification. Meanwhile, the parents educational qualification are categorized into : No formal education, elementary/primary education, high school education, finished secondary education, College/tertiary education, finished college or tertiary education. The result was $x^2 = 31.435$; and $p = .026$.

Table 7: Relationship of students' academic performance and parents' educational qualification.

Parameters		Level of Academic Performance				x^2	p
		Fairly Satisfactory (75-79)	Satisfactory (80-84)	Very Satisfactory (85-89)	Outstanding (90-100)		
Education	No Formal Education	1	4	11	1	31.435	.026
	Elementary/Primary Education	0	5	8	5		
	Finished Elementary Education	0	0	5	2		
	High School / Secondary Education	1	10	4	7		
	Finished Secondary Education	0	10	10	4		
	College/Tertiary Education	1	3	9	10		
	Finished Tertiary Education	0	4	4	11		

Note. $x^2 = Chi-square value$

**Significant at $p < 0.05$*

C. Relationship of Students' Academic Performance with Parents' occupation.

Meanwhile, parents occupation is categorized into government employee, OFW, Farmer or fisherfolk/ businessman, vendor/ salesperson and others. The result was $x^2 = 17.975$; and $p = .264$.

Table 8: Relationship of students' academic performance and parents' occupation.

Parameters	Level of Academic Performance				x ²	p	
	Fairly Satisfactory (75-79)	Very Satisfactory (80-84)	Satisfactory (85-89)	Outstanding (90-100)			
Occupation	Government Employee	1	4	9	11	17.975	.264
	OFW	1	1	3	2		
	Farmer/Fisher Folk	1	14	18	6		
	Businessman	0	4	8	3		
	Vendor/Salesperson	0	6	5	9		
	Others	0	7	8	9		

Note. x² = Chi-square value

**Significant at p<0.05*

DISCUSSION

This section discusses the results on the exploration on the relationship of students' academic performance with the parents' socio-economic status. This also highlights the profile of the respondents and the significant difference of students' academic performance according to the respondents' profile.

A. Students' Demographic Profile

Gleaning from the table 1, the majority 80 (62.3%) of the Grade 11 students' parents' monthly income were P5,000.00 and below; while, 18 (13.8%) of them have an income of P5,001.00 – P10,000.00. Meanwhile, 11 (8.5%) generate money of P15,000.00 – P25,000.00. Also, 10 (7.7%) parents have P25,000.01 – P50,000.00, while 7 (5.4%) of them have P10,001.00 – P15,000.00. And only 3 (2.3%) of the parents belong to have an income of P50,001.00 and above. Hence, it can be interpreted that most of the students' parents have a monthly income of P5,000.00 and below.

As to the parents' educational attainment, majority of 24 (18.5%) managed to finish the secondary education, the 23 (17.7%) of them have college or tertiary education. The 22 (16.9%) got the high school or secondary education, while 19 (14.6%) finished the tertiary education. Furthermore, 18 (13.8%) of the parents only have the elementary or primary education, with 17 (13.1%) have no formal education. And only 7 (5.4%) finished the elementary education. Therefore, this can be deduced that educational attainment of majority of the parents only finished the secondary education.

In terms of the occupation, the majority of 39 (30.0%) parents were farmers or fisher folks, while 25 (19.2%) served as government employees, with 24 (18.5%) parents with specified jobs other than mentioned. Meanwhile, 20 (15.4%) worked as vendors or salesperson, and 15 (11.5%) of them were businessman. And only 7 (5.4%) parents were OFW. Thus, the findings concluded that majority of the parents were farmers or fisher folks.

The findings denote that majority of parents' income generated ranging between P5,000.00 and below. Corollary to this result, Delelis (2019) found that 35.87% of the respondents from College students of BS Accounting Information System of Cagayan State University – Andrews Campus belonged to the households whose monthly income, falling between P5,001.00 and P15,00.00, deemed as insufficient to meet both demands of the students' families and academic duties. Furthermore, majority of the educational attainment of the parents only managed to finish the secondary education, while the occupation were farmers or fisher folks. Kwarteng (2022) corroborates in their study on JHS students in the Upper West Akim District in Ghana that 80% of their parents has either no formal education or only managed to finish basic secondary education, whilst 70% were farmers at the same time.

B. Level of the Students' Academic Performance

Based on Table the overall mean of the students' academic performance is 87.71% with a verbal description of Very Satisfactory (85-89). This implies that the Grade 11 students of Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School have performed very well, thus, meeting the satisfactory grades in school.

Anent this finding, several scholars have defined and characterized academic performance as determining factor of a student's capacity for academic success. According to Kirschner and Karpinski (2010), Academic performance is determined by the number of hours studied per week and Grade Point Average (GPA) In addition, Yusuf, et al. (2016) pointed out that it is a student's observable and quantifiable behavior throughout a given time period. Furthermore, it encompasses a student's performance on assignments, assessments, midterms, simulated tests, and final exams.

C. Difference on the Students' Academic Performance According to Parents' Socioeconomic Status

This section provides a discussion on the significant difference on students' academic performance with the socio-economic status of their parents which includes the monthly income, educational qualification and parents' occupation.

C.1 : Difference of Students' Academic Performance and Monthly Income

In Table 3, a one-way ANOVA was employed to assess the difference between parents' monthly income and students' academic performance. The findings revealed that

there was a significant difference between the two variables, $F(5, 124), p = .014$. The hypothesis which states that “there is no significant difference on the academic performance of the students when they are grouped according to parents’ monthly income” is hereby rejected. This implies that academic performance of the students varies significantly according to the parent’s monthly income. The higher is the income, the higher is the academic performance. While students whose parents were having lower income have also performed low academically.

This finding is reinforced by Masereka et al. (2023) in their study on Influence of the Family Income on Academic Performance Among Secondary School Students of Kitwamba and Rugendabara-Kikongo Town Councils in Uganda. The result showed a significant difference wherein students from wealthier family outperform those students from lower income households.

C.2 : Difference of Students’ Academic Performance and Parents’ Educational Attainment

As illustrated in Table 4, a one-way ANOVA was employed to assess the difference between parents’ educational attainment and students’ academic performance. The findings revealed that there was no significant difference between the two variables, $F(6, 123), p = .099$. This denotes that regardless of their parents’ educational attainment, the students’ academic performance is almost the same.

This finding is supported by the study of Mohammad Ali et al. (2021), that 63.8% respondents from Yobe State, Nigeria’s Government Day Junior Secondary School in Gashaka that their parents’ educational attainment has minimal to no effect on their academic performance.

C.2 : Difference on the Students’ Academic Performance and Parents’ Occupation

As depicted in Table 5, A one-way ANOVA was employed to assess the difference between parents’ occupation and students’ academic performance. The findings revealed that there was no significant difference between the two variables, $F(5, 124), p = .113$. The sig. value accepted the null hypothesis of the study stating that “there is no significant difference on the academic performance of the students when they are grouped according to parents’ occupation”. This means that the students’ academic performance would remain the same even when their parents have varied occupation.

Relative to this finding ,however, Kamal et al. (2022) stated that between students whose parents reported being less involved in their education, the former group showed greater academic success across all subject areas due to the higher occupational background of the students.

D. Relationship Between Students' Academic Performance and Parents' Economic Status

This section discusses the relationship of students academic performance and parents' economic status in the contest of their monthly income, educational attainments and parents' occupation.

D.1 : Relationship of Students Academic Performance and Parents' monthly income

As presented in Table 6, a Chi-Square Test of Association was employed to assess the relationship between parents' monthly income and students' academic performance. The findings revealed that there was a significant relationship between the two variables, $\chi^2(15, N=130) = 26.095, p = .037$. This portrays that the performance of the students has a relation to their parents' monthly income.

In this regard, Ogunshola (2019) also found the relationship of the income to the academic performance of the students in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council in Nigeria. This led to a conclusion that income may influence the performance of the students in school.

D.2 : Relationship of Students Academic Performance and Parents' Educational Attainment

In table 7, Chi-Square Test of Association was employed to assess the relationship between parents' educational attainment and students' academic performance. The findings revealed that there was a significant relationship between the two variables, $\chi^2(18, N=130) = 31.435, p = .026$. Therefore, the degree of education that the parents have has relationship to the academic performance of the students.

Similar to this finding is the study of Hussain (2020) were 88% students from Government Secondary School of District Mardan, showed a consistent relationship between performance in school and their parents' educational attainment. This implies that depending on the degree of the education that their parents have, students' performance in school may vary significantly.

D.3 : Relationship of Students Academic Performance and Parents' occupation

Based from Table 8, a Chi-Square Test of Association was used to assess the relationship between parents' occupation and students' academic performance. The findings revealed that there was no significant relationship between the two variables, $\chi^2(15, N=130) = 17.975, p = .264$. This finding shows that, students' performance academically would remain constant without the connection from their parents' occupation. Although, there were few available related studies that could support this finding, therefore further study is needed concerning this matter.

Conclusions

Based from the findings, this study concluded that majority of the respondents were from low-income families having a P5,000.00 and below monthly income, with their parents finishing secondary education who were farmers or fisher folks. And that the students' academic performance has an association to income in which grades of the students with parents who have average income of P5,000.00 and above are significantly high when comparing from lower income of P5,000.00 and below. Educational attainment also has a relationship but there was no difference on the academic performance of the students. While there was no significant difference and relationship between the academic performance to the occupation of the parents.

Recommendations

1. Schools can use the findings of this study as a basis in advocating for strengthened supports and resources for students from low-income families, especially those whose parents are working in underrepresented occupations such as agriculture, to improve student academic performance.
2. Students are recommended to continue striving for high grades and teachers are encouraged to implement support strategies to maximize and further improve the academic performance of students from diverse socioeconomic status.
3. Governments can also use the research findings of this study as a basis for implementing policies or programs to reduce financial inequality and provide support to families with low financial incomes to help the parents meet the students' educational needs.
4. Schools may also establish scholarship opportunities specifically tailored for students with parents of lower educational attainment and introduce supplementary resources, such as tutoring services or access to educational materials, for students facing financial problems.
5. Future researchers are recommended to use this study in order to explore additional information to validate and give more accuracy to the present findings of this study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Since this study is trying to analyses the relation between the academic performance of Grade 11 STEM students at MSU-Sulu Senior High School and the socioeconomic status of their parents, respondents were informed about the study's objectives. Proper ethics and protocols were observed during the data gathering of researchers. Participation was voluntary and ethical standards such as welfare, rights and privacy of the information taken were prioritized. Any results and findings obtained by the researchers were highly preserved with confidentiality with utmost capability.

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